

Role of Age, Education and Marital Status on Family environment among adults

Chanda Yadav¹; Dr Lokesh Gupta²

¹Department of Psychology Ph.D. Scholar, Amity Institute of Behavioural & Allied Sciences, Amity University Haryana, India

²Department of Psychology Assistant Professor Scholar, Amity Institute of Behavioural & Allied Sciences, Amity University Haryana, India

Corresponding Author Email: chanda.om123@gmail.com

Abstract— Background- Families are the main social group in which people discover their sense of self and drive to survive. The term "family" refers to a group of people who are related through marriage, blood relations, or adoption. The family members live under the same roof as one another and share a same environment. They engage and communicate as a group when playing roles such as a husband and wife, mother and father, son or daughter, etc. Even though the connections between people, families, societies, cultures, and civilizations are complicated and changeable, this unit shares several traits with all societies.

Aim & Objective-To see the effect of age, education and marital status on family environment among adults.

Material and method- Total 100 adult participants, age 18 to 60 years (mean age 32.84 and SD 8.27) were taken through purposive sampling. They were compared with age, education and marital status. Tools included a personal data sheet, which was used to collect socio-demographic information and personal data pertinent to the current situation, including name, age, gender, education, occupation, marital status, religion, place of residence, family type, family size, and family environment scale.

Result- family environment was assessed in 8 different areas of adult participants. It was found that difference observed on the basis of education in two dimension- Relationship dimension (conflict) and Personal growth dimension (reactive-recreational orientation) low score of graduate participants indicates that they are not expressive and low in personal growth as compare to post graduate participants. Difference was also observed in married and single participants in relationship dimension (Cohesion, expressiveness and conflict). Findings suggests that single has highly cohesive and expressive as compared to married participants and married Has high conflict as compared to single. Findings also suggests that participants having age between 18 to 30 years highly expressive as compare to age range of 31 to 60 years.

Conclusion- It can be concluded that age, education and marital status may affects person's relationship and personal growth.

Keywords: Family environment, Relationship, personal growth, Education, age and marital status.

I. INTRODUCTION

The institution of the family faces numerous strains from modern life that constantly threaten its ability to survive and adapt. Family is regarded as a very crucial aspect influencing a child's development because it serves as the child's primary socialization unit (Ozcinar, 2006). The patterns of interaction and behaviour of the family members play a vital role in the behaviour and adjustment patterns of an individual (Leary, 1995). Parents who are friendly with their children provide information about how people deal with one another in a social situation, follow certain procedures, and engage in cooperative behaviour (Lindsey et al., 1997).

The foundation of the unit, the family, has been impacted in the current situation as a result of various changes to various aspects of our family system, such as working parents, increased nuclear families, urbanization, mobilization, the technological revolution, and the influence of Western culture. The modern process introduces numerous issues, anxieties, and concerns into human existence that have a negative impact on fundamental family values like spending quality time together, sincerity, morality, and humanity. It has also been observed that there has been a significant shift in human civilization. Due to increasing urbanization and technology, man has lost his identity and has become a part of the social machine (Dagar & Dull, 1994). Adolescents must learn how to cope with psychological stress, peer pressure, deal with emotions, resolve conflicts, build bridges with friends, family, and school, develop self-confidence, protect themselves from high-pressure marketing strategies, particularly those employed by the alcohol industry, and cope with other stresses such as academic competition and a hankering for material gains and these all necessitate having good mental health (Malhotra & Gupta, 2014). Research shows that those adolescents show more success in life who belong to households in which parents are both supportive and are accepting the child's needs for more psychological independence (Olsson et al., 1999; Madhu & Matla, 2004; Powell, 2006; Lee et al., 2006; Deepshikha & Bhanot, 2011).

Numerous elements, such as the type of family constellation, the number of children in the family, the marriage of the husband and wife, the employment of the mother or father, and the socioeconomic and religious background of the family, all have an impact on the family environment.

Some studies were found related to demographical variable based on gender, family environment and anxiety disorder and academic achievement.

II. AIM- To see the effect of age, education and marital status on family environment among adults.

III. OBJECTIVES

- To see the effect of age (18 to 30 Years & 31 to 60 Years) on family environment among adults.
- To see the effect of education (Graduate & Post Graduate) on family environment among adults.
- To see the effect of marital status (Married & single) on family environment among adults.

IV. HYPOTHESIS

- There would be a significant difference of age (18 to 30 Years & 31 to 60 Years) on family environment among adults.
- There would be a significant difference of education (Graduate & Post Graduate) on family environment among adults.
- There would be a significant difference of marital status (Married & single) on family environment among adults.

V. SAMPLE A total of 100 adults with age range of 18 to 60 years were recruited from healthy population. After a thorough explanation of the study's objectives, all participants signed written informed consent forms.

VI. DESIGN- Current research has been taken up by using cross sectional study design.

VII. TOOLS

VII.I. PERSONAL DATA SHEET: Personal information relevant to the current situation, such as name, age, gender, education, occupation, marital status, religion, place of residence, family size, and family members, will be collected using a personal data sheet.

VII.II. FAMILY ENVIRONMENT SCALE: Family Environment Scale developed by Harpreet and Chadha (1993). The scale consists of eight dimensions like Cohesion, Expressiveness, Conflict, Acceptance and caring, Independence, Active recreational orientation, Organization and Control. This scale has the reliability of 0.87 and a validity of 0.82 and hence it will use in its original form.

VII.III. ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

Before the study begins the researcher was given outline to the participants about what the research is, and then ask their consent (permission) to take part. Information was given to the participants regarding purpose of the research. They were assured about confidentiality will be maintained. The participants have the right to move out of the research at any point of time.

VII.IV. DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS The data collection has been completed from Delhi NCR region by contacting one to one person. A safe, secure, controlled and comfortable environment has been provided to develop working rapport and filled out the form from the subject. Data analysis has been done by descriptive and inferential analysis methods using Excel and SPSS software.

VIII. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table-1

An independent-samples t-test conducted to compare the participants on family environment by age

S No	Dimensions of family environment	Area of family environment	N	Age Groups	Mean±SD	t	p-value	Effect size
1.	Relationship Dimensions	Cohesion	43	Age 18-30 years	52.60±3.71	1.769	.080	0.34
			57	Age 31-60 years	51.46±2.77			
2.		Expressiveness	43	Age 18-30 years	32.77±3.33	2.044	.044	0.40
			57	Age 31-60 years	31.53±2.73			

3.		Conflict	43	Age 18-30 years	42.72±3.58	1.806	.074	0.36
			57	Age 31-60 years	44.00±3.44			
4.		Acceptance and caring	43	Age 18-30 years	46.02±3.90	0.524	.601	0.10
			57	Age 31-60 years	46.39±3.02			
5.	Personal Growth Dimensions	Independence	43	Age 18-30 years	32.02±3.46	1.141	.256	0.22
			57	Age 31-60 years	31.28±3.02			
6.		Active-Recreational Orientation	43	Age 18-30 years	29.19±3.17	0.887	.377	0.17
			57	Age 31-60 years	29.74±2.99			
7.	System Maintenance Dimensions	Organization	43	Age 18-30 years	8.26±.81	0.893	.374	0.18
			57	Age 31-60 years	8.07±1.16			
8.		Control	43	Age 18-30 years	14.58±1.69	0.758	.450	0.15
			57	Age 31-60 years	14.86±1.90			

Statistically significant difference was found in the area of expressiveness ($p < 0.04$). Higher score (32.77 ± 3.33) of aged between 18 to 30 years adult shows more expressiveness as compared to lower score (31.53 ± 2.73) of aged between 31 to 60 years.

Table-2

An independent-samples t-test conducted to compare the participants on family environment by education-

S No	Dimensions of family environment	Area of family environment	N	Education Groups	Mean±SD	t	p-value	Effect size
1.	Relationship Dimensions	Cohesion	48	UG	52.15±3.28	0.084	.934	0.01
			45	PG	52.09±3.28			
2.		Expressiveness	48	UG	31.98±2.99	0.239	.812	0.04
			45	PG	32.13±3.23			
3.		Conflict	48	UG	42.73±3.60	2.556	.012	0.53
			45	PG	44.53±3.17			
4.		Acceptance and caring	48	UG	45.71±3.59	1.721	.089	0.35
			45	PG	46.93±3.24			
5.	Personal Growth Dimensions	Independence	48	UG	31.29±2.75	1.688	.095	0.34
			45	PG	32.40±3.55			
6.		Active-Recreational Orientation	48	UG	28.83±3.04	2.648	.010	0.55
			45	PG	30.47±2.89			
7.	System Maintenance Dimensions	Organization	48	UG	8.19±0.81	0.145	.885	0.02
			45	PG	8.16±1.27			
8.		Control	48	UG	14.56±1.61	1.154	.252	0.24
			45	PG	15.00±2.03			

Significant difference was found in the areas of conflict ($p < 0.01$) and active recreational orientation ($p < 0.01$) indicates low score (42.73 ± 3.60) was found in relationship dimension (conflict) of UG adults reflects that they have less amount of openly expressed aggression and conflict among family members as compare to PG adults (44.53 ± 3.17). Difference was also observed in personal growth dimension (active-recreational orientation). Low score (28.83 ± 3.04) of UG adults indicates that they are less participate in social and recreational activities as compared to PG adults (30.47 ± 2.89).

Table-3

An independent-samples t-test conducted to compare the participants on family environment by marital status-

S No	Dimensions of family environment	Area of family environment	N	Education Groups	Mean \pm SD	t	p-value	Effect size
1.	Relationship Dimensions	Cohesion	63	Married	51.41 \pm 2.76	2.200	.030	0.43
			37	Single	52.86 \pm 3.80			
2.		Expressiveness	63	Married	31.56 \pm 2.60	2.196	.030	0.43
			37	Single	32.92 \pm 3.57			
3.		Conflict	63	Married	43.97 \pm 3.36	1.933	.056	0.39
			37	Single	42.57 \pm 3.72			
4.		Acceptance and caring	63	Married	46.43 \pm 3.05	0.757	.451	0.15
			37	Single	45.89 \pm 3.97			
5.	Personal Growth Dimensions	Independence	63	Married	31.22 \pm 2.98	1.539	.127	0.31
			37	Single	32.24 \pm 3.54			
6.		Active-Recreational Orientation	63	Married	29.73 \pm 2.99	0.978	.330	0.20
			37	Single	29.11 \pm 3.19			
7.	System Maintenance Dimensions	Organization	63	Married	8.08 \pm 1.09	0.895	.373	0.19
			37	Single	8.27 \pm 0.90			
8.		Control	63	Married	14.89 \pm 1.85	1.073	.286	0.22
			37	Single	14.49 \pm 1.72			

Statistically significant difference was found in the areas of cohesion ($p < 0.03$) expressiveness ($p < 0.03$) and conflict ($p < 0.05$). The married adults' low cohesiveness score (51.41 \pm 2.76) reveals that they have lower levels of commitment to, and support from, their families as compared to single (52.86 \pm 3.80). On the other hand, low score on expressiveness also suggests that married adults have Less encouragement to family members to act honestly and freely express their feelings and views as compared to single. Higher score on conflict of married adults shows they are rich amount of openly expressed aggression and conflict among family members as compared to single adults.

IX. DISCUSSION

Very few studies were found related to demographical variables among adults on family environment. A study done by Seema et al., (2023) with 300 adolescent (150 males and 150 females) explored that significant difference was found in all areas of Family environment scale as the values of t-test on academic achievement show that female adolescents have a significantly higher level of academic achievement as compared to male, female adolescents noticed a higher level of Cohesion in the family as compared to male adolescents, female adolescents were found more openly expressed environment in the family to express aggression and conflict as compared to male adolescents, female adolescents feel unconditionally accepted and caring by their families as compared to male adolescents, female adolescents were found actively participating in social and recreational activities as compared to male adolescents. Another study conducted by Umashankari & Vasumathi, (2023) a negative correlation between the two variables (family environment and the level of anxiety) was found which indicates that a positive family environment reduces the level of anxiety experienced by adolescents. Some other study reveals that the adolescent experiencing healthy family environments are found to have higher academic achievement in comparison to children belonging

to low family environment. (Kumar & Lal 2014) The result of the present study shows that significant difference was found in age on family environment in relationship dimension. Individual (age range 18-30 years) rich to encourage family members to act openly and express their feelings and thoughts directly, however individual (age range 31-60 years) are less competent for the same. In the same way significant difference was found in education on family environment. Individual having UG level of education are less amount of openly display hostility and disagreement among family members however individual with PG level are highly expressive of aggression and conflict. It may be due to overburdened, lots of responsibilities, expectation of family members and others etc. due to which highly qualified individuals may more expressive for conflicting situations. On the other hand, findings suggest that highly qualified individuals are involved in social and recreational activities whereas UG level of individuals are less participative in social and recreational activities.

When married and single individuals compared on family environment it was found that single individuals are more committed, helping, supportive and also encourage family members to express their feelings and thoughts directly as compared to married people. Findings shows that married people are more expressive their aggression and conflict among family members as compared to single.

X. CONCLUSION

Over all findings suggests that people when increasing their qualification and got married become more vulnerable toward aggression and conflict as compared to low qualification and single individuals. It also can be concluded that individual with higher qualification is more sociable and creative.

XI. IMPLICATIONS

There is a paucity of studies related to socio-demographical variables on family environment and also the findings of present study compelled researcher to do thorough study for the same.

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